

Data Science in Astronomy: Detecting Gravitational Lensing with ML

What types of astronomical data exist and how can insights be derived from it?

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ABSTRACT

In reference to Fluke et al., we take a closer look at the current state of Data Science Methods used in the field of Astronomy and give an overview of their application. The available data can essentially be categorized into five different domains (images, spectroscopy, photometry, catalogues, simulations), for which different data science methods can be applied. We will go into more detail on the maturity in each of these and point towards the relevant research papers. We will provide further depth by looking at the research done by Huang et al., which managed to approximately double the number of known strong gravitational lenses at the time of publication in 2021. This was achieved by using a deep residual neural network on the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument Legacy Survey Data (DESI), which covers roughly a half the sky.

KEYWORDS

data science, astronomy, gravitational lensing

1 Introduction and Background

Historically, astronomical research has always had a strong emphasis on cataloging and classification of objects in the sky. Charles Messier published his famous catalogue in 1771, where he was both describing and classifying what he observed through his optical telescope. Using the stars to predict future events has an even longer history. Advances in physics have made it possible to predict the movement of stars, planets and even galaxies. Alas the computational effort these models require is tremendous and has always been a limiting factor [2].

Today, the volume and complexity of the data in Astronomy is staggering. If we take the data release from the Panoramic Survey Telescope and Rapid Response System (Pan-STARRS) as an example, we are dealing with nearly 2 petabytes of data [4]. Future surveys will likely be in the exabyte range. Analyzing this data quickly and effectively is a considerable

challenge where methods used in Data Science can be put to the test adequately.

1.1 Types of data in Astronomy

According to Fluke et al. there are five domains of data in Astronomy [1]:

Images – are a well-known form of astronomical data where light is collected through a telescope and stored as a pixel grid of numerical intensity values. Most observations are done using the visible and the infrared spectrum.

Spectroscopy – are high resolution measurements of the light spectrum which informs astronomers about the chemical composition as well as the physical properties of an object, like temperature or density.

Photometry – is a secondary data product which measures the intensity and variation of light (flux) of an object. This enables researchers to create light curves which can be used to identify extra solar planets and variable star types, as well as determining relative distances.

Catalogues – are products of the data gathering. They usually consist of collections of tables containing categorial or numerical data and have a mix of subjects like star clusters, galaxies, or planetary nebulae.

Simulations – are the result of applied theory. When theoretical astronomical models are combined with computational methods, they form a visual description of the underlying mechanisms. The movement of celestial object relative to each other or the formation of galaxies would be common examples.

1.2 Data Science Techniques in Astronomy

Computers have been used to process astronomical data from very early on. In the 70's, John von Neumann's supercomputer "MANIAC" was used to calculate stellar evolution codes and used roughly half of its total cycles [5]. Data Science offers tools that can go past the automatic processing of data and enable researchers to derive insight in the process. We want to give just a few examples of methods used [1].

In 2019, Masters et al. used SOMs (self-organizing maps) to derive physical properties of galaxies from photometric data. As a class of unsupervised neural network SOMs reduce the dimensionality of the data, without losses in the topology [6].

Vasylenko et al. used GANs (Generative Adversarial Networks) in 2018, to restore galaxy distribution data behind the Zone of Avoidance, an area of the sky, where the galactic plane and dust obscure and filter objects behind it [7].

GANs in general have a bright future in Astronomy and are already being used to calculate the distribution of dark matter in simulations of gravitational systems [8].

Since images are a very common in this field, CNNs have also made a big impact. The number of images in modern sky surveys are only increasing and getting more and more detailed, this trend is most likely to continue. Wu et al. used CNNs to predict galaxy metallicity and outperformed RFs (Random Forests) with their approach. [9]

The increasing popularity of these methods can, at least partially, be attributed to the advances in GPUs and their widespread availability since GPUs cut the processing time significantly.

Of course, there are many more examples of data science methods and Fluke et al. give a good overview of the commonly used methods and the fields where they are applied.

Nature/type	Cn	R	Cg	F	G	D	I
Image	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Spectroscopy	•	•	•			•	•
Photometry	•	•	•	•		•	•
Light curve	•	•				•	•
Time series	•	•	•			•	•
Catalogue	•	•	•	•		•	•
Simulation	•	•			•	•	

Figure 1: The table represents a qualitative summary of publications from 2017-2019. Columns are Classification, Regression, Clustering, Forecasting, Generation, Discovery, and Insight [1]

2 Application of data science in Astronomy

Let's have a closer look at one research project, which serves as a great example of the impact ML-Methods can have on astronomical research. Huang et al. performed a semi-automated search for strong gravitational lensing in the DESI Data Release using a deep residual neural network [3].

2.1 Gravitational lenses

The great Albert Einstein himself theorized about the existence of gravitational lenses, when he formulated his theory of general relativity, hence they are also known as "Einstein-Rings". He realized that gravitation would not only act on matter but also on light. As a result, large masses, like a galaxy for example, will change the path of light passing by them. To any observer this would look like a ring of sorts that forms around the mass.

Figure 2: Illustration of the physics behind Einstein-Rings

Figure 3: Image of a gravitational lens

His theory was confirmed in 1987 with the help of the VLA (Very Large Array). Gravitational lenses can be used to calculate mass distributions in the universe and therefore may help us understand dark matter and dark energy better [3].

2.2 Gravitational lens detection with ResNet

The DECaLS Survey is part of the DESI Legacy Release and contains pictures taken by a terrestrial telescope. This survey covers half of the sky and contains pictures of several bands of the light spectrum. Their first test set consisted of around 423 known lenses and 13.000 non-lens images. For a neural net this can be considered a very small set and previous approaches had to rely on simulated lens-images. They

increased the amount by including less strong candidates and had 760 lenses in their training set in the end. After assembling the trainings data, they split the data 70:20:10 for testing and validation. They improved upon the ResNet from Lanusse et al. which used Theano and Lasagne libraries and implemented it in TensorFlow. They also augmented the 101 x 101 pixel images by rotating, mirroring, zooming, etc. For training they ran 120 epochs with a cross entropy loss function [3].

Figure 4: Training/Validation loss [3]

Figure 5: AOC false positive Rate [3]

Figure 6: Examples of grade A lens-candidates in DESI; red square means they were previously known to be lenses [3]

After minor adjustments they used their model on the DESI Data Release and if a gravitational lens was detected a human inspector confirmed the result [3].

In the end they managed to identify about 1200 new lenses and effectively doubled the number of known lenses at the time of publication. Thus, a machine learning algorithm identified more lenses than all scientists combined previously.

3 Conclusion

The field of Astronomy offers many data related challenges which manage to effectively put new data science methods to the test. While the data sets which modern surveys generate today, are only growing larger and larger, Data Science is also becoming more and more efficient. They can not only be used to automate a lot of the data processing but also help to generate new insights.

Technical advances in computing (faster GPUs) and astronomy (better telescopes and space probes) complement each other very well and the resulting images and simulations are growing more and more detailed and comprehensive. Looking at them alone can foster curiosity and wonder.

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